

Fate and Future of Optical Sensing in PA

Nicolas Tremblay*, Kosal Kuhn, Philippe Vigneault
Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada/Agriculture et Agroalimentaire Canada

Remote sensing of crops is an important tool for exploiting the opportunities offered by precision agriculture. Some unresolved issues are preventing the technology from achieving its expected potential.

Remote sensing is a powerful tool that allows farmers to quickly assess the status and spatial variability of their crops as well as to make spatially variable applications of inputs in fields. The potential of variable-rate applications is often mentioned but seldom demonstrated successfully as it requires a quantitative, not just descriptive, assessment of the canopy. Since precision agriculture is seen as a way to improve the productivity and sustainability of agricultural operations in the future, it is a good time to take an overall look at the achievements, limitations and potential of optical remote sensing.

Reflectance-based remote sensing is widely used, with a diversity of platforms and spatial resolutions available to practitioners. Typically, the information that is generated consists of vegetation indices, which are related to the amount of vegetation (more specifically, the presence of chlorophyll) present in a unit surface area. This amount may vary according to differing densities of chlorophyll in leaves or differing quantities of leaves with the same density of chlorophyll. A large number of vegetation indices have been developed to enable optimal quantification of vegetation in most circumstances; however, all of the indices are affected by signal saturation problems in conditions of high canopy density. Some empirical models can make good use of the raw assessment provided by vegetation indices. To increase quantitative interpretation and better support complex and predictive models, two key parameters can be derived from optical sensing: chlorophyll concentration and above-ground biomass. These are functional entities that can drive process-based model calculation. Unfortunately, chlorophyll and biomass are complex variables which cannot be differentiated with certainty using optical sensing.

Alternative or complementary techniques such as UV-induced fluorescence can be used to quantify pigments and components that are indicative of stresses. Passive fluorescence can be used to estimate photosynthetic performance. The increased spatial resolution provided by unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) may permit a breakthrough in biomass quantification. Their ability to gather very high resolution images and to cover many angles opens the door to 3-D reconstruction of canopies and therefore provides an alternative means of estimating biomass.

Precision agriculture is a management strategy that uses a wide range of technology to gather and process data for the purpose of guiding targeted actions that improve the precision, efficiency and productivity of agricultural operations. It should be kept in mind that agricultural production is characterized by considerable spatial and temporal variability and a great deal of uncertainty.

Precision agriculture has to operate in the context of genetics \times environment \times management (G \times E \times M) interactions. Optical sensing is just one of the technologies at our disposal to better assess the status of the systems we need to manage in a profitable and sustainable manner. It is our responsibility to understand its possibilities and limitations. It is also our responsibility to explore the other sources of data (soil, weather, economics, social) that are needed to refine the (process-based or artificial intelligence-based) predictive models that are badly needed to improve precision agriculture performance worldwide.